

Run-Time Detection of Malicious behavior based on Exploit Decomposition using Deep Learning: A feasibility study on SysJoker [★]

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Abstract. As malicious operations become gradually very complex and involve advanced attack campaigns even on embedded systems and IoT, there is an increasing need for detecting malicious behavior on a system as it dynamically as it happens. In this paper, a Deep Learning based malicious behavior dynamic, run-time detection methodology is proposed that rely on the collection of Linux OS execution flow metrics/features like CPU, disk and memory usage and their association with ATT&CK MITRE knowledge base exploits. Using that approach, we can emulate the attack sequence of complex malicious activity and use the collected features to train Deep Learning models in order to classify execution operations at run-time as malicious or not. In the paper, we provide a feasibility study of the proposed solution based on the ATT&CK MITRE exploit attack graph emulation of the SysJoker backdoor malware and we train several Deep Learning models acting as classifiers. The provided results showed that in SysJoker use-case study of the proposed approach we managed to obtain more than 99% accuracy and less that 0.5% False Positive and False Negative Rates.

Keywords: Malicious Behavior Detection · Deep Learning · Embedded System.

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity threats and eventually attacks constitute a very common encounter over the highly interconnected digital world of today. Through out the Internet, a system can be attacked by a very broad number of maliciously behaving entities from hackers (white hat or black hat one) to rogue Malicious software (malwares) or Advanced Persistent Threat (APT) campaigns that employ a plethora of different means to achieve their short or long-term goals. Typically, all malicious attacks are based on exploits of specific threats that appear in one way or another in a system. Eventually, such exploits are captured,

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documented and potentially mitigated so as to no longer become usable but this doesn't guarantee that mitigation measures are applied everywhere, in time and in the proper manner. Thus, from the moment an exploit on a system is discovered till the moment that all associated systems manage to remove this exploit, a non-trivial amount of time may pass thus leaving a system open to malicious attacks that use the exploit. The malicious behaviour landscape becomes even more complex by taking into account that malicious entities use a combination of mutating exploits to achieve their goals and that they also have the means to hide themselves to avoid detection by obfuscating their "signature". Thus, the potential malicious behavior detectors, have to extract from various system sources "breadcrumbs" of information to identify such behaviors and respond to them. Since this process can become highly complex and elusive, modern tools adopt Machine or Deep Learning (ML/DL) to improve the detection process.

The Malware detection research landscape constitute an indicative example of the existing approaches on malicious behavior identification. Malicious software, commonly known as Malware, are unsolicited installed software that are specifically designed to disrupt, damage or provide unauthorized access to third parties. Types of malware include, but are not limited to, viruses, worms, Trojan horses, ransomware, APTs and spyware. Different types of malware have unique traits, characteristics, employed exploits and manner of attacking a system. Timely malware and their malicious behavior detection is of crucial importance as the severity and impact of current and new malware can affect not only individuals but also to local and global economy [14] and even in healthcare due to disruption of public goods and services [18]. Finding new ways to detect malicious code has been an active area of research since the early 90's, with attempts such as [9]. Since then, the field has expanded with many more new and innovative approaches [12]. Analyzing a malware can be done in a static, dynamic or hybrid way. Static methods rely on an analysis of the malware executable code in order to discover static API call sequences from the Portable Executable file structure of a program and then using ML/DL classifiers to be able to associate this with known malwares. There can be a broad range of API Calls that can be monitored [13] to increase the accuracy as well as reduce the False Positive (FPR) or False Negative Rate (FNR) of the classification, however, all static detection methods can potentially fail when advanced malware or malicious behaviors in general are applied by an attacker [12]. Characteristic examples are polymorphically, oligomorphically or metamorphically operating malwares that alter their behavior over time and have their binary code obfuscated (so their binary cannot be analyzed).

Dynamic methods on the other hand consider the malware or in general the actor performing a malicious activity as a black box and observe its behavior from the outcomes of this activity. For malware detection using dynamic methods, sandboxes are typically used in an effort to monitor the malicious activities by logging system calls, dynamic API calls (eg. using DLLs), Hardware Performance Counters (HDC) [17] or other leaking information (eg. network traffic, memory dumps etc.) [13]. However, these techniques by using sandboxes are not

generally applicable to malicious behavior detection like APTs since sandboxing has a narrow scope (focused mostly on malware detection) and is not very realistic in complex attack campaigns (since practically you cannot sandbox an entire system). This highlights the need for a dynamic but also run-time detection procedure that relies on what can be measured on an actual system and not on a fully controlled sandbox.

Analyzing collected dynamic system information for malware detection is significantly assisted by ML/DL solutions. One popular approach derives from the capability of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) of predicting new states/events from a time-window of existing events so as to identify expected malicious behavior from existing dynamic behavioral data (mostly API Calls and/or System Calls) [15]. To this end, LSTM and GRU based solutions have been proposed, some times in combination with Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) [8] to provide accurate classification. Furthermore, CNN based solutions in combination with simple ML classifiers have also been used in the recent research literature especially in the IoT-embedded system domain [16]. The process of detection can also be enhanced by performing proper feature selection techniques that in combination with various classifiers can increase accuracy like the work in [11] where Reinforcement Learning is used in order to choose the proper features dynamically collected from a system to perform classification. Furthermore, there are also proposals for DL malicious behavior detection and analysis that rely on other DL models like autoencoders or DNNs with several layers that also provide very good results [12].

ML and DL techniques require significant amount of data in order to perform malicious behavior classification (e.g. malware classification). There are two different data mining methods used in the research literature for extracting usable features. Dataset generation for ML/DL training can be done by using the n-gram model or the graph model [15] as follows:

- **n-gram model:** The malicious behavior related features are collected in sequence and form separate time series flows that can be used collaboratively. Eg. measuring API Calls, System calls, CPU/Memory usage over time etc.
- **graph model:** The malicious behavior related features are collected and appointed as nodes in a graph so as to include the control flow of the malicious behavior in the data analysis.

From the above discussion, it becomes evident that the malicious behavior (and similarly a malware) detection and analysis procedure significantly depends on the proper "decomposition" of the malicious behavior. Depending on the analysis approach, static, dynamic or hybrid, the malicious behavior decomposition may involve its breaking up into a series of API Calls, or System Calls or specific assembly instructions or DLL usage etc. However, even if placed into a graph form, these metrics constituting the malicious activity decomposition are a fine-grained, structured, collection of primitive measurements that include apart from useful information also a lot of 'noise'. Potentially, though, a higher level, more refined decomposition could be made by documenting the exploitable activities (or exploits) that a malicious entity is bound to perform in order to mount an

attack (or an attack campaign). Such exploits have been thoroughly codified, categorized and documented in open access repositories like the ATT&CK MITRE knowledge base [5]. In [10] some first attempt to employ ATT&CK MITRE in an Android Malware has been made. In this work, the authors have connected malware actions with the specific macro tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTP) enumerated in the ATT&CK MITRE ontology in an effort to better describe the malware behavior. The authors use though a sandbox environment to collect TTPs as primitive metrics and associate them with a control flow graph (CFG) that they then use in order to create a Graph Neural Network (GNN) to classify Android Malwares. The [10] methodology can be considered a hybrid dynamic/static based approach and therefore it does need information from the Android APK to reconstruct the malware CFG.

1.1 Contribution

In this paper, a novel approach on DL based malicious behavior/malware detection is proposed that rely on metrics/features that can be collected from a real, non sandboxed, system and can provide classification of malicious activity that can be associated with the ATT&CK MITRE various reported exploits. In our proposed approach, in contrast to other solutions which either need pre-existing datasets or need to collect data by monitoring specialized features (eg. API or System calls) that are collected in sandbox environments, we rely on leaking information associated with the day-to-day operation of a system (especially of an embedded system) like CPU load, memory activity, disk load etc. Furthermore, in this paper a high level malicious activity decomposition is proposed that rely on the modeling of this activity (eg. an advanced malware) as a series of ATT&CK MITRE exploits taking place during the malicious activity. More specifically, the paper’s contribution is summarized as follows:

- A DL based methodology is proposed for designing and implementing a runtime, dynamic, malicious behavior monitoring system applicable in Linux OS based desktop and embedded systems that rely on easy-to-collect metrics and the ATT&CK MITRE exploits. The proposed approach covers all design aspects of such system including the proper dataset collection, the feature engineering procedure to be followed (feature selection and normalization) as well as the DL models and classifiers selected, trained and used for inference. In order to detect complex malicious behavior the proposed methodology relies on DL based identifying of ATT&CK MITRE exploits in the actual computation flow of a Linux OS device as this is described by its CPU load, its memory usage and its disk utilization.
- An n-gram model based dataset generation approach for malware and/or malicious behavior detection ML/DL training is proposed as part of the above methodology. The approach manages to produce features in an efficient and risk-free manner, by emulating the malware’s/malicious behaviour through its ATT&CK MITRE decomposition and produce features by monitoring the Linux OS execution environment.

- Three DL classifiers (FCN, CNN, RNN/LSTM models) that can support the above methodology are compared/evaluated and the best approach for accurate training and validation is proposed in terms of achieved Accuracy, FPR and FNR.
- The advanced backdoor malware SysJoker has been used as a use case feasibility validation of the proposed methodology. Using the proposed methodology and the selected DL classifier we managed to provide sysJoker detection accuracy of 99.51% with FNR and FPR of 0.23% and 0.47% respectively (using an LSTM classifier).

2 Malware decomposition and Attack Vector Data collection

2.1 Attack Model

In the proposed paper solutions, we assume that an attacker is capable of mounting advanced attacker campaigns that include various attack vectors. This includes a series of malicious related activities that are based on the exploits as those are documented in the ATT&CK MITRE Knowledge base. A significant part of the attacker's activities are focused on the installation, establishment, lateral movements and command and control capabilities of advanced malware as those can be manifested in backdoors, ransomware and APTs.

The attacker's goal is to eventually establish command and control of a Linux OS device whether this device is a desktop PC or an embedded system Linux OS IoT device. While Desktop PC infiltration and control remains a viable attacker option, in our attack model the focus is on embedded Linux OS IoT devices and networks. We assume that the benign processes that are running on the Linux OS IoT embedded system device implement some closed control loop operations that involve sensing and actuation and they constitute predictable, repetitive processes. We also assume that the attacked device is connected to the internet and that there is an established remote access control mechanism for authenticated users. We also assume that the IoT device target has a REST API that can be used to handle GET and POST messages to it. The above capabilities can be exposed to the attacker and can be part of the attacker's attack vectors. We also assume that all attacks that are performed in the attacker's campaign are based on exploits of ATT&CK MITRE Knowledge base. However, the resulting malicious activities including the design, implementation and deployment of advanced malwares are not necessary already documented in MITRE or Virus Total databases.

2.2 Analyzing Malware Components: SysJoker Use Case

To provide a working proof-of-concept, we opted to focus on one use case, malware SysJoker, for which there is currently no known publicly available dataset. SysJoker [7] is a backdoor malware, discovered in December 2021 by Intezer,

a software company. SysJoker is a multi-platform system malware, capable of infecting Windows, Linux and MacOS.

SysJoker masquerades as a system update and generates its own Command and Control (C2) domain registrations by decoding a string which is retrieved from Google Drive. Based on Intezer's [4] and VirusTotal technical analysis, the malware is written in C++ and performs differently based on the target OS.

According to AttackIQ's [3] SysJoker Attack Graph, what is most interesting is the correlation between the malware's behavior and the techniques defined in the MITRE knowledge based.

The publicly available attack graph [3] for Linux starts with Technique T1105 (Ingress Tool Transfer). This technique allows adversaries to transfer tools or files from an external system into the compromised environment. SysJoker uses this technique to download and save samples to disk.

Next, SysJoker executes two discovery commands to get system information using technique T1033 (System Owner/User Discovery) where an adversary attempts to identify the primary user by getting account information. SysJoker uses the **id -u** and **whoami** commands.

Technique T1033 is followed by T1564.001 (Hide artifacts: Hidden Files and Directories) where the malware create hidden files and folders to evade detection. SysJoker renames specific files and folders with the prefix character ".".

Following T1564.001, SysJoker establishes persistence into the system using Technique T1053.003 (Scheduled Task/Job: Cron) by creating a recurring execution of its code into Linux's cron utility and then execute Technique T1059.004 (Command and Scripting Interpreter: Unix Shell) which misuses the Linux shell and executes the **nohup** command to execute silently.

Once running silently, SysJoker then retrieves the system's network information with Technique T1016 (System Network Configuration Discovery) by running the **ifconfig** command to find the local IP and MAC addresses of the system.

Having discovered the system's networking information, SysJoker then goes on to collect system information using Technique T1082 (System Information Discovery), by executing the **uname -rms**

Finally, since SysJoker is not by default set up to communicate with a specific C2 server, it needs a text file hosted on Google Drive, which will contain a token that will specify the C2 server. SysJoker uses Technique T1102.001 (Web Service: Dead Drop Resolver), which describes how to use a legitimate web service to host information about the C2 server and download it.

Once the C2 server configurion has been setup, Sysjoker then uses Technique T1071.001 (Application Layer Protocol: Web Protocols) to transfer all commands and response traffic to and from the C2 server using HTTP POST and GET requests.

SysJoker uses a number of different Techniques in a specific order to operate.

2.3 Proposed Malicious Behavior Detection Methodology

Figure 1 showcase the proposed methodology. Our intention is to create a generic methodology that can be applied into any number of malware and will be able to generate new datasets to train ML/DL models by emulating malicious behavior.

Initially the malware has to be statically analyzed to determine what API calls are made and how it operates. This analysis is necessary to decompose the correlate all types of APIs into MITRE Techniques. This step will generate the attack graph, which will defines the sequence of the aforementioned Techniques.

Having defined all necessary Techniques, the next steps include running the emulation of the malware by implementing and executing the attack graph while in parallel monitor the system. Once all the tests have been completed data from both the monitoring system as well as the malware emulation are combined into a labeled dataset.

Finally the regular ML/DL process begins by performing the necessary feature engineering, such as feature selection and scaling followed by the training of the AI/ML model itself. Finally, once the model is trained it can be deployed in a new system.

Fig. 1: Proposed Methodology

2.4 Proposed Dataset collection

To generate our dataset we deployed one Virtual Machine with Linux as the Operating System to emulate an Linux-enabled embedded system. For our initial tests, we didn't generate any workload on the system and left it idle, apart from the malware techniques invocations and the monitoring tools.

For metric collections on the system, we employed the use of Glances [6]. Glances is a cross-platform monitoring tool, written in python, that uses the **psutil** library to extract a large number of system metrics, such as CPU, memory usage and load of the machine. The sampling frequency we opted to use is 100 milliseconds, which is one parameter of Glances. The metrics were extracted into a CSV file, using the Glances command line interface **glances**.

To execute the emulation of SysJoker on the system, we utilized Atomic Red team [2]. Atomic Red Team is a library of tests mapped to the MITRE ATT&CK framework in order to testers to quickly test their environments by emulating

attack Techniques without negatively affecting their systems. The library is comprised of a number of tests for various Techniques, often more than one per Technique, each one tailored to specific OS. Each test contains the necessary script or code to be compiled on the target system and the test’s requirements. Each test also contain a yaml file with machine readable instructions on how to install the test’s requirements, compile the test test, run as well as cleanup after the test is complete in order to return the system to its original state.

For our purposes we wanted to be able to execute a number of Techniques in a sequence, as discussed in section 2.2, to emulate the SysJoker attack. We wrote a python script that made use of the atomic-operator [1] python package, which can read the Atomic Red Team’s yaml files and perform the tests.

Operationally, we executed each Technique in the order defined by the attack graph and our script wrote down the time the attack started and the time the attack ended in a csv file. We executed a large number of attacks with a time delay between them. To avoid having the AI/ML model memorize the time delay between the tests, we opted to randomize the time delay between the tests from 40 to 60 seconds.

After running our tests, we combined the Glances output CSV with the test’s CSV, via a python script to automate the process of generating the final dataset. While the Techniques are running we label each row with the value of **1**, else with the value of **0**.

Before training our AI/ML training we needed to perform a set of feature engineering steps, specifically feature selection and scaling, more commonly known as normalization. As Glances can provide a vast number of features, a small number of them happen to have zero variance , such as `cpu irq` and `cpu.guest_nice`, which we removed them from the dataset. As for scaling, we performed the basic normalization process with mean and standard deviation as discussed in section 3.1.

The goal of our ML/AI application is to be able to read system metrics and be able to correctly classify whether there is series of Techniques running and therefore the presence of a malware. We used offline learning, creating the dataset and then perform batch learning.

The final dataset contains 257118 row entries, with the 7% labels with the value of 1 and 93% with the value 0. The features of the dataset is depicted in Table 1.

3 Proposed Deep Learning Approach

Deep learning models have been widely adopted for various problems, and have proven to be especially powerful tools for anomaly detection and classification, particularly in areas such as image and signal processing.

In the this section, we analyze the problem formulation and the preprocessing phase of our dataset in order to achieve the best possible performance. Subsequently, we present a deep learning approach for anomaly detection and classification using three types of Neural Networks, a Fully Connected Network

Table 1: Dataset Features

Feature	Description	Unit
cpu.total	Total CPU usage	Percentage
cpu.user	Time spent in user space	Percentage
cpu.system	Time spent in kernel space	Percentage
cpu.idle	CPU used by any program	Percentage
cpu.iowait	Time CPU waited for I/O completion	Percentage
cpu.ctx.switches	Number of CPU context switches	Integer
cpu.interrupts	Number of interrupts per second	Integer
cpu.soft_interrupts	Number of software interrupts per second	Integer
mem.available	The total amount of available memory	Bytes
mem.percent	Memory percentage usage	Percentage
mem.used	Total memory used	Bytes
mem.available	Total amount of available memory	Bytes
mem.free	Amount of memory not being used	Bytes
mem.inactive	Memory marked as not used	Bytes
mem.buffers	Cache for files, such as file system metadata	Bytes
mem.cached	Cache for various things	Bytes
mem.shared	Memory which can be simultaneously accessed	Bytes
load.min1	Average sum of processes waiting over 1 minute	Float
load.min5	Average sum of processes waiting over 5 minutes	Float
load.min15	Average sum of processes waiting over 15 minutes	Float
Label	1 if SysJoker is running, 0 if not	Integer

(FCN), a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network.

3.1 Problem Formulation and Preprocessing

For an AI/ML model to be properly trained, the dataset must be organized effectively. The dataset consists of 257,119 timestamps. Each timestamp is recorded from Glances with a sampling rate of 100 milliseconds and after an initial feature selection we focused on 20 features. We divided the dataset into three sets, training, validation and test set. The training set consists of 164,446 timestamps, the validation set contains 141,140 and the remaining 53,423 are assigned to the test set.

Since the dataset consists of time series data, it is recommended to operate in a time window frame. This approach is proposed for time series classification because it can easily capture time dependence patterns among the timestamps of the same input. The inputs that are passed to the corresponding neural network have dimensions of $(WindowSize, NumberOfFeatures)$. Each input $X[t - WindowSize : t, :]$ is trained to target the $Y[t]$ value. At each step, the window shifts down by $StepSize$ timestamps and constructs the next input.

The tuning parameters we selected, as common, between the implemented models are 128 as the batch size, the Adam optimizer, a learning rate of $10e-4$ and a step size of 1.

Preprocessing plays a pivotal role in readying data for utilization in machine learning and deep learning models. One of the crucial preprocessing steps is data standardization, also referred to as normalization. This process involves re-scaling the features of a given dataset to have zero mean and unit variance.

The standardization process consists of two primary steps. Initially, the mean and standard deviation for each feature must be calculated. Following this, for each data point in the feature, the mean is subtracted from the corresponding value, and the resulting value is divided by the standard deviation.

3.2 Fully Connected Network Approach

The Fully Connected Network (FCN) approach is a type of artificial neural network that has been widely used in machine learning for solving binary classification problems. In an FCN, each neuron in one layer is connected to every neuron in the next layer. This approach was implemented mainly to obtain a baseline performance score in order to be outperformed by the more advanced models (CNN and LSTM).

The structure of the corresponding Fully Connected Neural network is described at Table 2. First, the 2D input need to be vectorized. If the shape of input is (WindowSize, NumberOfFeatures), the corresponding vector shape is (WindowSize X NumberOfInputs, 1). The first layer is a Dense Layer of 128 neurons, followed by a Dropout layer. Dropout is a regularization technique used in neural networks to prevent overfitting. This Layer gets the outputs of the previous layer and and drops the to zero based on the rate variable. All the Dropout layers of this approach has been set to drop 50% of the input.

Table 2: FCN model

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Number of Params(78,750)
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 400)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	53888
<i>dropout</i> ₁ (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
<i>dense</i> ₁ (Dense)	(None, 128)	16512
<i>dropout</i> ₂ (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
<i>dense</i> ₂ (Dense)	(None, 64)	8256
<i>dense</i> ₃ (Dense)	(None, 1)	65

Next, the same technique is adopted as before. A second Dense layer of 128 neurons is followed by Dropout layer of 50% rate. This is a common technique where numerous hidden layers have the same number of neurons until the network needs to gradually reduce its dimensionality.

Then, a third Dense layer is placed of 64 neurons. Lastly, a single neuron layer is necessary to predict a value between 0 and 1. All the hidden layers incorporate the *RelU* activation function. Only the last layer makes use of the *sigmoid* function.

3.3 Convolutional Neural Network Approach

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning model that has proven to be state-of-the-art solutions in addressing image and signal processing problems. Furthermore, CNNs have also been employed to solve binary

classification problems with time series data, since they can gradually capture abstract patterns that represent higher-level concepts.

A CNN architecture typically consists of one or more convolutional layers, where a set of filters are applied to extract features from the input data. These filters slide over the input data and perform element-wise multiplication and addition operations to generate a feature map. The resulting feature maps are then passed through pooling layers that downsample the output and decrease the number of parameters. Finally, the last layer of the CNN is flattened into a one-dimensional vector and fed into a fully connected neural network.

Table 3: CNN model

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Number of Params(22,657)
conv1d (Conv1D)	(None, 18, 32)	2048
<i>MaxPooling1d(MaxPooling1D)</i>	(None, 9, 32)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 288)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	18496
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
<i>dense₁(Dense)</i>	(None, 32)	2080
<i>dense₂(Dense)</i>	(None, 1)	33

In this subsection, we present a detailed description of the structure of our CNN-based approach in Table 3. The model begins with a single 1D CNN that employs 32 different filters with a kernel size of 3. The stride of each kernel was set to 1 and no padding was selected. Subsequently, a MaxPooling layer was applied to reduce the parameters by half. Then, a flatten layer was placed to vectorize the output of the previous layer.

Next, a Dense layer of 64 neurons was applied, followed by a Dropout layer with a drop rate of 50%. Finally, a Dense layer of 32 neurons was placed, followed by a single neuron layer to obtain the predicted value. The intermediate Dense layers were activated by the ReLU function, and the single neuron output layer was activated by the sigmoid function.

3.4 Long Short-Term Memory Neural Network Approach

LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) is a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) that has proven to be highly effective in processing sequential data, especially in the case of time-series data. LSTM networks are particularly efficient for this type of problems because they are able to capture long-term dependencies in the sequence of the input data, avoiding at the same time the problem of vanishing gradients that can occur in traditional recurrent neural networks. This is achieved through the utilization of a memory cell that is able to selectively gather past information.

Typically, an LSTM based neural network is followed by a Fully Connected network which gradually reduce its dimensional until a single neuron is placed at the output in order to predict an anomaly ($i=0.5$) or not($j0.5$). This technique was adopted for the presented approach.

Table 4: LSTM model

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Number of Params(11,137)
lstm (LSTM)	(None, 32)	6912
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	2112
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
<i>dense₁</i> (Dense)	(None, 32)	2080
<i>dense₂</i> (Dense)	(None, 1)	33

A detailed structure of the employed LSTM based network is being presented in Table 4. An LSTM layer consisted from 32 units is placed at the beginning. Then, a Dense layer of 64 neurons is added at the output of the LSTM layer. In order to prevent overfitting, a Dropout layer with drop rate of 50% is placed next. Subsequently, a second Dense Layer with the same number of neurons is added followed by a single neuron layer. The activation function of Dense layers is *RelU* except from the output neuron (last layer) which adopts the *sigmoid*.

4 Results and Analysis

A performance evaluation was made in order to find out if the proposed solutions of this paper could detect the anomalies (sysJoker attack) in the computer system. Various performance indices were employed to evaluate the effectiveness of our work such as false positive rate (FPR), false negative rate (FNR), and accuracy (ACY).

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (1)$$

FPR can be calculated using Eq.1 and express the rate that the proposed model classifies the sysJoker malware as normal. Here, the FP(False Positive) variable refers to the number of cases that are categorized as normal even though they were malware and true negative (TN) means the number of cases correctly classified as normal.

$$FNR = \frac{FN}{FN + TP} \quad (2)$$

FNR refers to the rate that normal cases are classified as malware. It can be calculated using 2. False negative (FN) means the number of cases that are incorrectly classified as sysJoker malware, even if they are normal cases, and true positive (TP) means the number of cases correctly classified as malware.

Finally, ACY which is calculated with using Eq3 and refers to the accuracy metric. ACY measures how accurately malware and normal cases are classified.

$$ACY = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (3)$$

The performance evaluation of all three models are presented in Table 5. All models were evaluated using time window sizes of (20,20), (40,20), and (60,20).

Table 5: Model results

Window Size	FCN			CNN			LSTM		
	FPR	FNR	ACY	FPR	FNR	ACY	FPR	FNR	ACY
(20,20)	0.0001	0.6781	0.9443	0.0006	0.2004	0.9829	0.0088	0.0705	0.9862
(40,20)	0.0001	0.7426	0.9390	0.0032	0.04344	0.9935	0.0157	0.0561	0.9809
(60,20)	0.002	0.7860	0.9356	0.0129	0.0806	0.9815	0.0023	0.0347	0.9951

The FCN model demonstrated a good performance in terms of false positive rate (FPR), however, it showed a significant deficiency in terms of false negative rate (FNR). Specifically, the model with the time window size of (20,20) was found to be the most efficient in terms of accuracy, with an overall accuracy of 94.43%. However, this model predicted 67.71% of sysJoker malware timestamps as normal, which results a non-reliable model. The high value of FPR contributed mainly to the overall accuracy of the model

(a) CNN Training Loss and Accuracy

(b) CNN Validation Loss and Accuracy

Fig. 2: CNN measurements

The model CNN achieved an FPR, FNR, and ACY of 0.06%, 20.04%, and 98.29%, respectively, with a window size of (20,20). Using a window size of (40,20), the FPR improved to 0.32%, but the FNR decreased to 4.3%, which

is significantly better than the 20.04% achieved by the (20,20) window size. Moreover, the test accuracy score was 99.35% for this window size. However, increasing the window size to (60,20) did not result in better performance, as the FPR and FNR scores were 1.29% and 8.06%, respectively, while the accuracy metric dropped to 98.15%. The CNN model with a window size of (40,20) outperformed the (20,20) and (60,20) window sizes since it only classified 4.3% of malware timestamps as normal and 0.32% of normal cases as a sysJoker attack. Furthermore, the CNN model significantly outperformed any window size of the Fully Connected neural network. This outcome was expected because CNN networks can extract more efficient patterns than FCNs.

(a) LSTM Training Loss and Accuracy

(b) LSTM Validation Loss and Accuracy

Fig. 3: LSTM measurements

The LSTM model exhibited optimal results with a window size of (60,20), achieving the lowest FPR and FNR values of 0.23% and 3.47%, respectively, and the highest ACY value of 99.51%. In contrast to other models, the LSTM model achieved the worst metrics with a window size of (40,20), exhibiting a higher FPR of 1.57% and a higher FNR of 5.61%, leading to a lower ACY of 98.09%. The window size of (20,20) exhibited moderate performance with a FPR of 0.88%, a FNR of 7.05%, and an ACY of 98.62%. The LSTM based model with window size

(60,20) outperformed the CNN based model with time window (40,20) in terms of FPR, FNR and ACY by -0.09%, -0.87% and +0.16% respectively. Therefore, the LSTM model exhibited higher efficiency in all performance metrics compared to any other model used in this study. This behaviour was expected because LSTM models are able to collect the temporal dependencies that occur in time series data in a more sophisticated way.

All our models were fine-tuned to be trained for 40 epochs using a widely adopted technique called Early Stopping to prevent over-fitting. Early stopping continuously monitors the behavior of the loss function and updates the model's weights only when the loss function is reduced. Our results are presented in Fig.2a and Fig.2b, which illustrate the training and validation accuracy of the CNN based model for window sizes (20,20), (40,20) and (60,20) respectively. We observed that at epoch 29, the loss function reaches its minimum value and therefore, that model was obtained. Although there was greater variance among values in the validation phase, the differences remained 3%.

In a similar manner, Figures 3a and 3b showcase the training and validation phases of the LSTM-based methodology. It can be observed that the training loss reaches its minimum value at epoch 38. Moreover, based on the validation plot, the models with window sizes of (40,20) and (60,20) seem to capture the time-dependent patterns almost from the beginning of the validation. Conversely, for the (20,20) window size, at least 15 epochs are required for the accuracy metric to be stabilized,

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper a LDL based dynamic, run-time malicious behavior detection methodology was proposed using ATT&CK MITRE exploits based emulation of malicious operations that includes the collection of execution flow features from actual, non sandboxed, Linux OS Machines. A feasibility study of the proposed methodology was made using the SysJoker malware. The study aimed to implement and evaluate three deep learning solutions, each with three problem formulation approaches based on the selected shape of window size. These window sizes included (20,20), (40,20), and (60,20). The Fully Connected Network (FCN) was found to have poor performance based on the False Negative Rate (FNR) metric. The CNN model of window size (40,20) and the LSTM model of window size (60,20) were found to be reliable and efficient solutions. The evaluation of the three models was conducted using three performance indices: FPR, FNR, and ACY. The CNN model with a window size of (40,20) demonstrated a FPR of 0.32%, a FNR of 43.44%, and an ACY of 99.35%. Similarly, the LSTM model with a window size of (60,20) exhibited a FPR of 0.23%, a FNR of 0.47%, and an ACY of 99.51%. Overall, the LSTM model with a window size of (60,20) outperformed the other models implemented in this study in terms of FPR, FNR, and ACY indices. The findings suggest that the LSTM model with a larger window size is an effective solution.

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